

A Study of the History of Smallpox Vaccination in India

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ABSTRACT

The smallpox was extremely contagious and had no treatment. As early as 1325 BCE, cases of it were discovered through the research of Egyptian mummies. Variola, or "la variole," is another name for the smallpox. In earlier times, variolation was a common practice in Asia and several regions of Africa. This involved giving healthy individuals small amounts of material from smallpox lesions, which led to milder symptoms and a far lower mortality rate than a natural infection. According to certain reports, variolation practices date back to 200 BCE. Similar procedures were used in India by inoculation, where healthy children's skin was exposed to smallpox pustule material via a lancet or needle. According to accounts from the 18th century, this method has been used for many centuries. Smallpox is a dangerous viral disease, and from the 1800s through the mid-1900s, vaccination campaigns were conducted to prevent it. It used to have a major impact on India's health, but it has since been removed entirely. The National Smallpox Eradication Programme (NSEP) in India was established in 1962 with the primary goal of successfully eliminating smallpox from India within a short period of time. The NSEP effort successfully eradicated smallpox from India by the end of the 1970s. In this article discussed the smallpox and the importance of vaccination, the history of smallpox vaccination, how it was introduced to the people of India, and how it completely eradicated.

Key Words: Smallpox Eradication, Vaccination, National Smallpox Eradication Programme, Edward Jenner, Cow pox,

Smallpox

Smallpox is an acute contagious disease caused by the variola virus, a member of the orthopoxvirus family. It was one of the most devastating diseases known to humanity and caused millions of deaths before it was eradicated. It is believed to have existed for at least 3000 years¹. Smallpox is thus a filthy and loathsome disease. It may prove fatal, and even if the patient recovers, he may be left blind, marked with ugly pits, or defective in other ways. Smallpox is very infectious. It has been endemic in this country from time immemorial and is found all over the world, though practically all the civilized countries have almost banished it from their midst, or have made it more or less harmless by active and systematic preventive measures.

In India it appears also in severe epidemic form, and carries away men, women, and children, by thousands every year. No specific treatment has ever been discovered for the disease. The helplessness of the people in this country is apparent from the fact that they look upon it as goddess 'Mata' or 'Maharani' whom they propitiate by charms, incantations, and offerings². In India, as in many traditional societies, smallpox was often attributed to spiritual as well as physical forces. The pantheon of Hindu deities reflects a variety of divine attributes, and smallpox is traditionally regarded as the manifestation of one of the deities, the goddess Shitala, or Shitala-Ma, whose name means "the cool one", or "cooling mother". In southern India her name is Mariamma, in Maharastra it is Mata-May, in rural Bihar she is Bhagawathi, in Madhya Pradesh she is Maharani, and in areas of eastern India she is Ai. Other names for her include Devi Mata, Maha-Mai, and Jag Rani. In conventional Hindu theology, Shitala is one of seven sisters, each of whom is associated with different disease. These diseases commonly include chickenpox, measles, mumps, and cholera³.

Some of the most telling evidence for the prevalence of smallpox in nineteenth century India is however circumstantial rather than statistical. Pringle in 1869 estimated that in populous Doab, between the Ganges and Yamuna rivers of northern India, as many as ninety-five percent of the population were exposed to smallpox at some stage of life. Examination of prisoners, schoolchildren, and laborers in the 1870s in northern and eastern India largely confirmed this impression. Since smallpox erupted epidemically roughly every five to seven years in most parts

of India. Pringle maintained that “it has become quite a saying among the agricultural and even wealthier classes never to count children as permanent members of the Family until they have been attacked with and recovered from smallpox”. In a similar vein, Sir Sayyid Ahmad Khan, introducing a bill for compulsory vaccination in the Viceroy’s Legislative Council in 1879, said that smallpox was ‘the inevitable bridge which every child has to cross before entering into life; and recovery from the disease is considered second birth... Other diseases are looked upon as an accidental; but smallpox is regarded, as indeed it is, as almost universal. It touches the keenest of human susceptibilities; for there are thousands in this country who, though spared by it from death, still have traces of its violence in the deep marks on the face or the loss of an eye⁴.

Vaccination

Vaccination is one of the most cost effective interventions for the survival against several dreaded pathogens worldwide. It focuses on delivering for the benefit of the children and the pregnant women and the persons suffering from serious diseases. The effectiveness of the vaccination against polio, measles, diphtheria and others in India and other countries are well documented since 1798 when it first discovered against smallpox. Survey reports suggested that only 61% of all children received the vaccine each year. In India Universal Immunization Programme (UIP) and National Immunization Programme have set to immunize of the population. The objective of the programme is to increase the immunization coverage to improve the quality of service and to achieve self-sufficiency in vaccine production. According to the district level household survey, total of 53.5% coverage was done during the year 2007 – 2008⁵.

Smallpox Vaccination

The main goal of vaccination or immunization is to eradicate the infections from our society. Various research tools have been developed to eliminate effectively the disease causing agents and to increase the quality of the diagnosis. Smallpox was reported first in Goa, India, in 1545 AD as a killer disease in human may prevent the disease in future. Smallpox affected almost all races in the human history and its eradication technique was also practiced in Eastern world. In 1774, Benjamin Jesty of England inoculated the cowpox virus to his wife and children

and developed the smallpox vaccine. After few years, Edward Jenner, an English doctor investigated that mild cowpox virus develops mild disease but with no serious effect. However, this finding led him for the foundation of developing vaccine. The credit for developing smallpox vaccine was given to Edward Jenner in 1796. It is really unfortunate that the original inventor Jesty did not publicize his findings in 1774 which was twenty two years earlier than Jenner⁶. Edward Jenner's discovery of the cowpox vaccine in 1786 intensified the efforts to combat smallpox, and vaccination was introduced to large parts of the world within a few years. Although the spread of immunization against smallpox is commonly described as highly successful, the campaigns also represented an early encounter between an elitist state sponsored medicine and various forms of popular resistance⁷.

Weather condition of Indian sub-continent helps to multiply the growth of the agents of infectious diseases like measles, plague, hepatitis, and others. This continent is very large and thickly populated with 130 million people approximately. A large group of sections come under middle class and poor. Therefore, the socio-economic status is also very low among large group of people. Infectious pathogens are able to manifest diseases to create an epidemic situation. So, proper immunization has become mandatory to control the diseases.

In India the notion of popular resistance to smallpox prevention took a particular turn because variolation was well established in some regions – most notably Bengal – and here came to represent rival and not obviously inferior practice to vaccination. Based on the study of regions, the history of smallpox prevention in colonial India is often seen as consisting of two phases. Initially, the British looked with sympathy and even admiration on the “popular” Indian practice of variolation, but after the advent of vaccination they grew increasingly hostile and by the mid-nineteenth century variolation were described as “a murderous trade”⁸.

As early as 1802, the vaccine came to India and 3 year old Anna Dusthall, became the first recipient in Bombay. But the introduction of the vaccine was by no means smooth. There were traditional *Tilakadaars* who opposed it and frightened the local population, others opposed the vaccine's genesis from the cow and people were opposed to paying for a vaccine. The government responded in the 19th century by hiring ‘paid vaccinators’ and the vaccine was

administered through public dispensaries and touring vaccinators. This was perhaps the first public vaccination programme in India. Simultaneously variolation was banned by law⁹.

In the early part of British India, there was no certain policy for giving the vaccine to the people. Some migrant vaccinators travelled to the rural parts of India and vaccinated people sporadically. However, the percentage was very low at that time. The policy of vaccination was adopted in 1892 in India but in reality it was executed lately. In India during 1944 – 1945 the highest numbers of smallpox cases were reported. After independence, a maximum number of smallpox cases found in India.

India's National Smallpox Eradication Programme

In June 1959, one month after the decision of the Twelfth World Health Assembly to undertake a global eradication programme, an Expert Committee of the Indian Council of Medical Research recommended that a National Smallpox Eradication Programme should be established. The Indian Council of Medical Research set up a committee in May 1958 to examine the possibility of smallpox eradication, and the central government accepted its proposal that investigative pilot projects be set up across the country. Between 1960 and 1961, such projects were run in one district of each Indian state, which provided government officials at all levels of national administration with first-hand experience of many practical challenges. This work also helped the collection of the evidence base that justified by the launch of the National Smallpox Eradication Programme in January 1962¹⁰.

On September 9, 1970, the World Health Organization (WHO) and the government of India agreed upon a general plan of Operations for eradication of smallpox¹¹. The agreement was based upon the relationship between WHO and the government of India that was established in the basic agreement of July 16, 1952.

The objectives stated in the Plan of Operations were: 1. The eradication of smallpox by vaccination surveillance and containment measures and 2. The maintenance of achieved eradication.

One of the barriers to the successful implementation of the National Smallpox Eradication Programme was the quality of the vaccine and the method of delivery. Because of the World Health Organization's partnership, India was able to acquire higher quality freeze-dried vaccines. Concurrently, the quality of vaccine manufactured within India also improved. More problematic was the method of vaccination. Prior to 1969, the standard method of smallpox vaccination was to place a drop of vaccine on the patient's arm and press it into the skin with a single-point needle¹².

Zero smallpox

In May 1975, the very last case of smallpox was found in India. For the next two years, searches and active surveillance were continued to ensure there were no hidden smallpox pockets. In this phase of the programme, data was collected on the various rashes that health workers encountered in their field work. This led to the development of additional reporting documents, such as the Fever and Rash Outbreak Surveillance. This form required that each health worker report all cases of fever with rash, cases of and deaths due to chickenpox as well as cases of suspected smallpox.

From March to November 1976, 110 million households in more than half a million Indian villages and in 260 urban areas were searched for new smallpox cases¹³. Only cases of chicken pox were found.

In December 1976 and January 1977, a National Commission (including World Health Organization epidemiologists) visited all States and Union Territories of India, except the Andaman and Nicobar Islands, and scrutinized program activities. A few months later, in April 1977, the International Commission for the Assessment of Eradication of Smallpox in India visited the country, conducting its own evaluations in the field as well as reviewing the documentary evidence provided by the country.

The International Commission finally certified that India was free of Smallpox. Two years later, in December 1979, the Global Commission for the Certification of Smallpox Eradication declared that smallpox had been eradicated from the Planet.

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